

Analysis of Resilience of Family of Recipients of the Gemilang NTB Social Safety Net Program (JPS) During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this study is to figure out how resilient families who get the Gemilang Social Safety Net (JPS) are in terms of physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological and sociocultural resilience, and family resilience based on each type of work. Another part of this study will look at how income, the number of people living with you, and how many times you've been given JPS Gemilang affect your physical resilience. This is a quantitative study. The people who took part in this study were people who had JPS Gemilang stage III in the province of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB). Samples were chosen by a method called stratified random sampling. This study used the Treebox Method and multiple regression analysis to figure out how total income, number of dependents, and number of times receiving JPS Gemilang affected physical endurance, economic resilience, socio-psychological, and socio-cultural resilience, as well as how many times they were given the JPS Gemilang drug. According to a study done by looking at 100 samples, each person who gets JPS Gemilang has a high level of family resilience. This is true for the physical, economic, socio-psychological, and socio-cultural aspects that make up a person's family. All of JPS Gemilang are in the top group. It doesn't matter what job you do; your family is going to be able to handle it. People who work as professional staff, such as honorary teachers, honorary staff members, and teachers, do a lot of work that helps families be more resilient in general, but when they look at each of these things individually, they're in the middle. Physical resilience, economic resilience, socio-psychological and socio-cultural resilience don't seem to be affected by income, number of dependents, or number of times JPS Gemilang has been given to people. This is based on statistics.

KEYWORDS: Family Resilience, JPS Gemilang

INTRODUCTION

The spread of COVID-19 that has occurred in almost all parts of Indonesia has affected various aspects of life, be it the economic sector, education or the socio-economic conditions of the community. The government in anticipating and minimizing the spread of the Covid-19 virus continues to socialize so that people continue to maintain a healthy lifestyle and carry out social restrictions (social distancing) up to the Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB). The implementation of social distancing and PSBB that is carried out and continues to be emphasized by the government on the one hand can reduce the spread of the covid-19 virus, but it cannot be denied on the other hand that it has a negative impact on the stagnation of the community's economy, especially households, MSMEs, companies and finance (Apriyanti, 2020).

The President of the Republic of Indonesia issued Presidential Decree Number 12 of 2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters Spreading Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) as a national disaster. In line with this decision, the state has an obligation to provide good public services and is also obliged to meet the basic needs of its citizens (Law Number 25 of 2009). In this regard, the government is trying to help people affected by the spread of the COVID-19 virus with various policies, one of which is the Social Safety Net (JPS) program. The JPS program has actually been implemented by the government since Indonesia was hit by the economic crisis in mid-1977. Overcoming the economic crisis through the JPS program is very diverse, covering 17 sectors with a budget of Rp. 17,

The government again implemented the Social Safety Net program on April 2, 2020 to help communities affected by COVID-19 by providing assistance to 1.20 million Beneficiary Families (KPM), Basic Food Assistance in Jabodetabek for 3 months (April-June) outside of PKH recipients and Basic Food Cards, Cash Social Assistance, and Pre-Employment Cards as well as free electricity subsidies for 24 million households using 450 VA and a 50% discount for 7.2 million households using 900 VA.

Not only the central government, the JPS program is also implemented by various regional governments with various strategies and program implementation mechanisms, including the West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) provincial government. The NTB

Provincial Government upgraded the status of the emergency alert condition to emergency response with the signing of the Governor's Decree Number 360 – 405 of 2020 concerning the Status of Emergency Response to Non-Natural Disasters for Covid-19 in West Nusa Tenggara Province which came into effect on April 15 and will be extended according to conditions and developments which exists. In this decision, handling the health sector is a top priority, besides that the NTB Provincial Government has also implemented policies to mitigate the social and economic impacts of the pandemic, one of which is the Gemilang Social Safety Net (JPS) program.

The forms of assistance for the JPS Gemilang program are in the form of basic food assistance packages, supplementary assistance packages and other IKM/UMKM products, non-medical mask assistance packages for IKM/UMKM products, as well as other subsidy packages such as oil and gas fuel subsidy packages for fishermen and fish/food packages. for poor families. JPS Gemilang assistance recipients are based on village and kelurahan data for the poor and vulnerable to the poor in the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS) as well as other affected communities from sector/community proposal data (non-DTKS). The number of JPS Gemilang recipients is 350,000 families divided into 3 stages with the following details:

Figure 1. Number of JPS recipients for each stage

The JPS Gemilang program is held in 3 stages, with details of stage I as many as 105,000 Beneficiary Families (KPM) (99,000 DTKS and 6,000 non DTKS), Phase II as many as 125,000 KPM (110,119 DTKS and 14,881 non DTKS) and Phase III as many as 120,000 KPM (110,130). DTKS and 9,870 non DTKS). The distribution of the assistance package for phase III can be seen from Figure 2. It has been distributed 100% with a total of 110,130 DTKS packages spread over 10 districts/cities in the province of West Nusa Tenggara.

The distribution of the number of aid packages for each district/city in the province of NTB is relatively different, it is also adjusted to the percentage distribution of the population and the number of poor people in each district/city, where the largest number of JPS aid packages is East Lombok district, followed by Central Lombok and Bhima. JPS Gemilang assistance recipients are based on village and kelurahan data for the poor and vulnerable to the poor in the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS) as well as other affected communities from sector/community proposal data (non-DTKS).

The JPS Gemilang program is basically to help the poor and vulnerable poor and other affected communities to increase family resilience. Family resilience as a dynamic condition of a family that has tenacity, toughness, and physical, material, and mental abilities to live independently (Regulation of the Government of the Republic of Indonesia Number 21 of 1994). Seeing the JPS Gemilang program with various strategies, mechanisms and various products in an effort to meet the needs of people's lives, it is interesting to examine its impact in terms of the achievement of the program in increasing family resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of economic resilience, physical resilience, social psychological resilience. and socio-cultural resilience. In addition, to see also the relationship between the amount of income, the number of dependents and the number of times receiving assistance on physical resilience, economic resilience, socio-psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

JPS (Social Safety Net)Gemilang is an effort by the NTB Provincial Government to help meet the needs of the underprivileged community and empower the local economy with packages distributed to the community containing products produced by IKM and

MSMEs in NTB. The aim is to anticipate the socio-economic impacts arising from Covid-19, complementing the JPS of the Central Government. The form of the JPS Gemilang program is the recipient of village and kelurahan data-based assistance for the poor and vulnerable to the poor in the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS), while the goods in the JPS Gemilang program come from local SMEs/IKM products spread across 10 regencies/cities in the province. NTB. The policy was taken to maintain the existence of SMEs/IKM and maintain family resilience.

Family resilience (family strength or family resilience) is a condition adequate and sustainable access to income and resources for fulfill various basic needs including: food, clean water, services health, educational opportunities, housing, time to participate in society, and social integration (Frankenberger, 1998). Family resilience also has meaning as the ability of the family to develop themselves to live in harmony, prosperity and happiness outwardly and inwardly. In another view, family resilience includes the family's ability to manage resources and problems to achieve welfare (Sunarti, 2001). In line with Law Number 52 of 2009 family resilience can be measured using a systems approach that includes input components (physical and non-physical resources), family management processes (family problems and coping mechanisms), and outputs (fulfillment of physical and psycho-social needs).

Regulation of the Minister of PPPA Number 6 of 2013 concerning the Implementation of Family Development states that the concepts of resilience and well-being family includes: (1) Foundation Legality and Family Integrity, (2) Resilience Physical, (3) Economic Resilience, (4) Psychological Social Resilience, and (5) Social Resilience Culture. Therefore, the measurement of the level of family resilience will include the five things mentioned above, hereinafter referred to as measuring dimensions family resilience.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this study is a quantitative method. The population in this study were the beneficiaries of the JPS Gemilang program in the Province of NTB phase III, which were 110,130 recipients. The sample calculation was carried out using the Slovin formula with an error rate of 10%, so that 100 samples of JPS Gemilang beneficiaries were obtained. The method used in selecting the sample is stratified random sampling by determining the sample based on the number of recipients of JPS Gemilang in each district/city in the province of NTB. The data used in this study is primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to JPS Gemilang beneficiaries spread over 10 districts/cities in the Province of NTB.

This research was conducted with the aim of knowing the resilience of the families of the beneficiaries of JPS Gemilang in terms of physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic. To achieve the research objectives, the Tree-Box Method was used. This analysis is intended to provide an empirical description of the data obtained and to explain the characteristics of the variables studied. For data with an ordinal scale, the index value technique uses a scale of 1 to 4, so that the index of respondents' answers can be developed using the following formula:

$$((\%F1x1)+(\%F2x2)+(\%F3x3)+(\%F4x4)) \dots\dots\dots(1.1)$$

The next step, the index value is calculated by dividing the accumulated indicator value by the number of scales used. Criteria value range using three boxes (Tree-Box Method). According to Ferdinand (2012) Tree Box Method is divided into three categories, as follows.

- 10.00 – 40.00 = Low
- 40.01 – 70.00 = Medium
- 70.01 – 100 = Height

Furthermore, to see the effect of the amount of income, the number of dependents and the number of times receiving JPS Gemilang assistance on physical resilience, economic resilience, socio-psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience, multiple linear regression analysis was used. from normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Family Resilience Dimension

Based on the results of distributing questionnaires to the recipients of the JPS Gemilang program as many as 100 respondents spread over 10 districts/cities in West Nusa Tenggara Province, with the aim of the study being to see the resilience of the families of the recipients of the JPS Gemilang program from 4 main dimensions, namely physical resilience, economic resilience, socio-

psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience. Based on the results of the distribution of the questionnaire, a description of family resilience with 4 dimensions will be obtained using the tree box method with details of each dimension as follows:

Table 1. Physical Resilience of JPS Gemilang Program Recipients

No.	Indicator	Frequency				Total Score	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
1	With the existence of JPS Gemilang, it can meet the food needs of all family members	1	7	65	27	318	79.50%
2	With the existence of JPS Gemilang, it can meet the nutritional needs of the family	0	4	71	25	321	80.25%
3	By consuming JPS Gemilang products, you can strengthen your immune system	0	5	72	23	318	79.50%
	Average Physical Resistance	1	16	208	75		79.75%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Overall, the physical endurance of the recipients of the JPS Gemilang program is considered high because the index value is above 70, which is 79.75%. Furthermore, each indicator is also the same, namely high, where the highest index value is found in the JPS Gemilang indicator which can meet the nutritional needs of family members. Furthermore, the indicators for the JPS Gemilang Program can meet the family's food needs and products from JPS Gemilang that can strengthen the immune system have the same index value of 79.50% or quite high.

Then for the second dimension, namely economic resilience, it can be seen in table 2 with the following processing results:

Table 2. Economic Resilience of JPS Gemilang Program Recipients

No.	Indicator	Frequency				Total Score	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
1	With the existence of JPS Gemilang, you can reduce family expenses	0	5	66	29	324	81.00%
2	With JPS Gemilang, it can improve the family's economy	0	19	65	16	297	74.25%
3	Expenditures for necessities can be transferred to savings with the JPS Gemilang Program	0	23	61	16	293	73.25%
4	With the JPS Gemilang Program, it can meet the educational needs of families	0	34	52	14	280	70.00%
	Average	0	81	244	75		74.63%

Source: Primary Data Processed

The overall economic resilience of the recipients of the JPS Gemilang program is high with an index value of 74.63%. Then when viewed from each indicator there are 3 indicators that are classified as high, namely the existence of the JPS Gemilang program can reduce family expenses, the JPS Gemilang program can improve the family's economy and Expenditures for necessities can be transferred to savings with the JPS Gemilang Program with an index value above 70, where the highest index on the indicator with the JPS Gemilang program can reduce family expenses with an index value of 81.00%. Furthermore, there is 1 indicator that is classified as moderate with an index value of 70.00%, namely the existence of the JPS Gemilang program can meet the educational needs of the family.

The third dimension is psychological social resilience, where psychological social resilience consists of two main indicators, namely family harmony and family compliance with the law. The index value of each indicator is as follows:

Table 3. Psychological Social Resilience of JPS Gemilang Program Recipients

No.	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
1	With JPS Gemilang, it can strengthen family commitment	0	16	71	13	297	74.25%
2	Communication within the family and community is getting more harmonious with the JPS Gemilang program	0	17	71	12	295	73.75%
3	With the JPS Gemilang program, you can overcome emotional problems in the family	1	19	68	12	291	72.75%
4	Always think positive with the JPS Gemilang program	0	6	68	26	320	80.00%
5	Couples will be more attentive with the JPS Gemilang program	1	28	52	19	289	72.25%
	Average	2	86	330	82		74.60%

Source: Primary Data Processed

The social psychological resilience of the recipients of the JPS Gemilang program as a whole is in the high category with an average of 74.60%. Furthermore, for each indicator all fall into the high category, where the highest index value is found in the indicator of always thinking positively with the JPS Gemilang program with an index value of 80.00%. Next for indicators with the existence of JPS Gemilang can strengthen family commitment has an index value of 74.25%, the indicator of Communication in the family and society is more harmonious with the JPS Gemilang program with an index value of 73.75%, the indicator of the existence of the JPS Gemilang program can overcome emotional problems in the family has an index value 72.75% and lastly, the Pair indicator will pay more attention to the JPS Gemilang program which has an index value of 72.25%. Furthermore, for the last dimension, namely socio-cultural resilience, where the average index value as a whole is in the high category with an average of 71%. The details are as follows:

Table 4. Socio-Cultural Resilience of JPS Gemilang Program Recipients

No.	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
1	With the JPS Gemilang program I can help my closest family meet their needs (X41)	0	30	54	16	286	71.50%
2	With the JPS Gemilang program I can help the nearest community meet their needs (X42)	0	33	48	19	286	71.50%
3	With the JPS Gemilang program, I can participate in social activities (X43)	0	36	48	16	280	70.00%
	Average	0	99	150	51		71.00%

Based on table 4, there are two indicators whose index values are above 70.00%, and one indicator is below 70.00%. The indicators that fall into the high category are the JPS Gemilang program that can help the closest family meet their needs, the JPS Gemilang program can help the closest people meet their needs with the same index value of 70.50%. Furthermore, there is one index that falls into the medium category, namely the existence of the JPS Gemilang program that can make beneficiaries participate in social activities with an index value of 70.00%. Furthermore, the resilience of the families of the recipients of JPS Gemilang viewed in general from the 4 dimensions are as follows:

Table 5. Resilience of JPS Gemilang Recipient Families

No.	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
1	X11	1	7	65	27	318	79.50%
2	X12	0	4	71	25	321	80.25%
3	X13	0	5	72	23	318	79.50%
4	X21	0	5	66	29	324	81.00%
5	X22	0	19	65	16	297	74.25%
6	X23	0	23	61	16	293	73.25%
7	X24	0	34	52	14	280	70.00%
8	X31	0	16	71	13	297	74.25%
9	X32	0	17	71	12	295	73.75%
10	X33	1	19	68	12	291	72.75%
11	X34	0	6	68	26	320	80.00%
12	X35	1	28	52	19	289	72.25%
13	X41	0	30	54	16	286	71.50%
14	X42	0	33	48	19	286	71.50%
15	X43	0	36	48	16	280	70.00%
Family resilience index							74.92%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Based on table 5, it can be seen that the resilience of families receiving JPS Gemilang in West Nusa Tenggara during the pandemic is in the high category. This can be seen from the average family resilience index value of 74.92%. Judging from each dimension, it is also the same, namely the dimensions of physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological resilience and socio-culture are included in the high category because the index value is above 70.00%.

Family Resilience in terms of type of work

To see family resilience in terms of the type of work for JPS Gemilang recipients, this is done as an effort to determine the type of work that has high, medium or low family resilience during the pandemic for JPS Gemilang recipients. The types of work of JPS Gemilang recipients, which are summarized from the research questionnaire distributed, are as follows:

Table 6. Family Resilience Types of Work Rough Labor and Cleaning Workers Recipients of JPS Gemilang

Family Resilience Dimension	Indicator	Frequency				Total	Index
		1	2	3	4		
Physical Resistance	X11	1	1	17	10	94	81.03%
	X12	0	0	19	10	97	83.62%
	X13	0	0	20	9	96	82.76%
	Average index					287	82.47%
Economic Resilience	X21	0	1	14	14	100	86.21%
	X22	0	7	16	6	86	74.14%
	X23	0	8	15	6	85	73.28%
	X24	0	12	11	6	81	69.83%
Average index					352	75.86%	
Psychological Resilience Social	X31	0	6	18	5	86	74.14%
	X32	0	6	19	4	85	73.28%
	X33	0	6	19	4	85	73.28%
	X34	0	2	18	9	94	81.03%

	X35	1	8	15	5	82	70.69%
	Average index					432	74.48%
Socio-Cultural Resilience	X41	0	11	12	6	82	70.69%
	X42	0	11	11	7	83	71.55%
	X43	0	16	8	5	76	65.52%
	Average index					241	69.25%
Average Family Resilience Index							75.40%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Family resilience based on the type of work for manual labor and cleaning staff is relatively high overall, this can be seen from the index value of 75.40%. Furthermore, for each dimension, both the dimensions of physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological resilience and socio-culture are included in the high category as well. This type of work for manual labor and cleaning staff consists of laborers, casual daily laborers, scavengers and farm workers. In addition, the recipients of JPS Gemilang also consist of professional types of work, as for the details as follows:

Table 7. Family Resilience Types of Work Professionals Recipients of JPS Gemilang

Family Resilience Dimension	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
Physical Resistance	X11	0	0	5	1	19	79.17%
	X12	0	0	5	1	19	79.17%
	X13	0	0	0	6	24	100.00%
	Index Average					62	86.11%
Economic Resilience	X21	0	0	5	1	19	79.17%
	X22	0	1	5	0	17	70.83%
	X23	0	2	4	0	16	66.67%
	X24	0	4	2	0	14	58.33%
	Index Average					66	68.75%
Psychological Social Resilience	X31	0	0	6	0	18	75.00%
	X32	0	1	5	0	17	70.83%
	X33	0	1	5	0	17	70.83%
	X34	0	1	5	0	17	70.83%
	X35	0	3	3	0	15	62.50%
	Index Average					84	70.00%
Socio-Cultural Resilience	X41	0	2	4	0	16	66.67%
	X42	0	2	4	0	16	66.67%
	X43	0	3	3	0	15	62.50%
	Index Average					47	65.28%
Average Family Resilience Index							71.94%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Based on table 7, the average index of family resilience of professional workers is in the high category, but when viewed from each dimension, not all dimensions of family resilience of professional workers are in the high category. The dimensions of physical resilience are the only dimensions that fall into the high category, while the dimensions of social psychological resilience, economic resilience and socio-cultural resilience are included in the low category. Professional workers who received JPS Gemilang in this study were honorary teachers, Koran teachers and honorary staff.

In addition, the recipient of JPS Gemilang also consists of administrative services and sales personnel in shops and markets, the details are as follows:

Table 8. Family Resilience Types of Occupation of Service and Sales Administration Staff in Shops and Markets Recipient of JPS Gemilang

Family Resilience Dimension	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
Physical Resistance	X11	0	3	19	8	95	79.17%
	X12	0	2	21	7	95	79.17%
	X13	0	3	20	7	94	78.33%
	Index Average					284	78.89%
Economic Resilience	X21	0	1	21	8	97	80.83%
	X22	0	4	21	5	91	75.83%
	X23	0	8	17	5	87	72.50%
	X24	0	9	17	4	85	70.83%
	Index Average					360	75.00%
Psychological Social Resilience	X31	0	6	21	3	87	72.50%
	X32	0	6	21	3	87	72.50%
	X33	1	5	21	2	82	68.33%
	X34	0	3	21	6	93	77.50%
	X35	0	11	13	6	85	70.83%
	Index Average					434	72.33%
Socio-Cultural Resilience	X41	0	13	14	3	80	66.67%
	X42	0	14	13	3	79	65.83%
	X43	0	12	15	3	81	67.50%
	Index Average					240	66.67%
Average Family Resilience Index							73.22%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Family resilience, the type of work for service and sales clerks in shops and markets as a whole is in the high category with an average index value of family resilience of 73.22%, each dimension of family resilience from the dimensions of physical resilience, economic resilience and resilience. Social psychology is in the high category because the average index value is above 70.00% where the highest index is on physical endurance. On the other hand, the lowest index that falls into the medium category is socio-cultural resilience with an average index value of 66.67%. The types of service and sales administration workers in shops and markets in this case are market traders, grocery traders, massage therapists, food couriers, motorcycle taxis and security guards.

Table 9. Family Resilience Types of Work for Agricultural and Animal Husbandry Workers Recipients of JPS Gemilang

Family Resilience Dimension	Indicator	Frequency				Total value	Index Value
		1	2	3	4		
Physical Resistance	X11	0	3	24	8	110	78.57%
	X12	0	2	26	7	110	78.57%
	X13	0	2	26	7	110	78.57%
	Index Average					330	78.57%
Economic Resilience	X21	0	3	26	6	108	77.14%
	X22	0	7	23	5	103	73.57%
	X23	0	5	25	5	105	75.00%

	X24	0	9	22	4	100	71.43%
	Index Average					416	74.29%
Psychological Social Resilience	X31	0	4	26	5	106	75.71%
	X32	0	4	26	5	106	75.71%
	X33	0	7	23	5	103	73.57%
	X34	0	0	24	11	116	82.86%
	X35	0	6	21	8	107	76.43%
	Index Average					538	76.86%
Socio-Cultural Resilience	X41	0	4	28	7	120	85.71%
	X42	0	6	20	9	108	77.14%
	X43	0	5	22	8	108	77.14%
	Index Average					336	80.00%
Average Family Resilience Index							77.14%

Source: Primary Data Processed

Family resilience in the type of work for agricultural and livestock workers has an average index of overall family resilience of 77.14% and is classified as high. Each dimension of family resilience is included in the high category, where the highest average index is found in socio-cultural resilience. In addition to looking at the family resilience of each type of work based on the 4 dimensions of family resilience, it will also look at the relationship between the amount of income, the number of dependents and the number of times receiving JPS Gemilang on physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience of JPS Gemilang recipients. . Before the data is processed, the classical assumption test consists of normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test where the results are all data are normally distributed, multicollinearity does not occur and heteroscedasticity does not occur, the details are as follows:

Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Physical Endurance (Y1)

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 100		
Model	.818873549	3	.27295785	F(3, 96) = 0.47		
Residual	55.5800669	96	.57895903	Prob > F = 0.7029		
Total	56.3989404	99	.569686267	R-squared = 0.0145		
				Adj R-squared = -0.0163		
				Root MSE = .76089		

y1	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
x1	-5.25e-08	1.01e-07	-0.52	0.605	-2.53e-07	1.48e-07
x2	-.0480733	.0649847	-0.74	0.461	-.1770669	.0809204
x3	.0553973	.0919298	0.60	0.548	-.1270819	.2378765
_cons	3.984133	.1953399	20.40	0.000	3.596387	4.37188

Figure 2. Regression Results of Relationship between Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Physical Endurance (Y1)

Based on the results of data processing, it can be seen that all independent variables, both the amount of income (X1), the number of dependents (X2) and the number of times receiving JPS Gemilang (X3) partially have no significant effect on physical endurance, where the value of x1 is 0.605, x2 0.461 and x3 of 0.548 are above 0.05, or greater than 0.05. Likewise, simultaneously all the

independent variables x1, x2 and x3 together have no significant effect on the physical endurance of the JPS Gemilang recipient with a value of 0.7029.

Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Economic Resilience (Y2)

Source	SS	df	MS			
Model	.808562741	3	.269520914	Number of obs =	100	
Residual	43.6399225	96	.454582526	F(3, 96) =	0.59	
Total	44.4484853	99	.448974599	Prob > F =	0.6211	
				R-squared =	0.0182	
				Adj R-squared =	-0.0125	
				Root MSE =	.67423	

y2	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
x1	-5.18e-08	8.97e-08	-0.58	0.565	-2.30e-07	1.26e-07
x2	-.0147832	.0575829	-0.26	0.798	-.1290844	.099518
x3	.100041	.0814589	1.23	0.222	-.0616537	.2617358
_cons	3.391792	.1730905	19.60	0.000	3.04821	3.735374

Figure 3. Regression Results of Relationship between Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Economic Resilience (Y2)

Based on Figure 3 the regression results, it can be seen that the value of the variable x1 is 0.565, x2 is 0.798 and x3 is 0.222, this means that partially all independent variables do not have a significant effect on the economic resilience of JPS Gemilang recipients, as well as simultaneously do not have a significant impact on resilience. economy with a value of 0.6211.

Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Psychological Social Resilience (Y3)

Source	SS	df	MS			
Model	1.83267702	3	.610892339	Number of obs =	100	
Residual	48.8058692	96	.508394471	F(3, 96) =	1.20	
Total	50.6385462	99	.511500467	Prob > F =	0.3134	
				R-squared =	0.0362	
				Adj R-squared =	0.0061	
				Root MSE =	.71302	

y3	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
x1	1.48e-08	9.49e-08	0.16	0.877	-1.74e-07	2.03e-07
x2	-.0298766	.0608958	-0.49	0.625	-.1507539	.0910007
x3	.1305327	.0861455	1.52	0.133	-.0404648	.3015302
_cons	3.435236	.183049	18.77	0.000	3.071886	3.798585

Figure 4. Regression Results of Relationship between Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Psychological Social Resilience (Y3)

Based on Figure 4, all of the independent variables x1, x2 and x3 partially have no significant effect on the psychological social resilience of JPS Gemilang recipients because the t-count value is above 0.05. Likewise, simultaneously, all independent variables together do not have a simultaneous effect on the psychological social resilience of the recipients of JPS Gemilang.

Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Socio-Cultural Resilience (Y4)

Source	SS	df	MS			
Model	3.2637261	3	1.0879087	Number of obs =	100	
Residual	65.3200497	96	.680417185	F(3, 96) =	1.60	
Total	68.5837758	99	.692765413	Prob > F =	0.1947	
				R-squared =	0.0476	
				Adj R-squared =	0.0178	
				Root MSE =	.82487	

y4	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
x1	7.57e-08	1.10e-07	0.69	0.492	-1.42e-07	2.94e-07
x2	.0524338	.070449	0.74	0.459	-.0874064	.192274
x3	.1259821	.0996598	1.26	0.209	-.071841	.3238052
_cons	2.689198	.2117652	12.70	0.000	2.268848	3.109549

Figure 5. Regression Results of Relationship between Total Income (X1), Number of Dependents (X2) and Number of Times Received JPS Gemilang (X3) Against Socio-Cultural Resilience (Y4)

Based on Figure 5, it can be seen that partially all independent variables have no significant effect on socio-cultural resilience with a value of x1 of 0.492, x2 of 0.459 and x3 of 0.209 greater than 0.05. Simultaneously also the same, all independent variables together do not have a significant effect on socio-cultural resilience.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, using the treebox method, the results showed that the resilience of the families of JPS Gemilang recipients was generally in the high category during the pandemic, as well as each dimension of resilience of the families of JPS Gemilang recipients, namely the dimensions of physical resilience, economic resilience, social psychological resilience and resilience. Socio-cultural resilience is also included in the high category.

Meanwhile, when viewed in terms of the type of work, namely the type of work, manual labor and cleaning staff, family resilience is included in the high category in general and based on each dimension. The type of service administration work and sales in shops and markets also fall into the category of high family resilience in general, while for each dimension, 3 dimensions fall into the high category, namely physical resilience, economic resilience and social psychological resilience and 1 dimension is included in the high category. medium with an index value of 66.67%. For the type of work in agriculture and animal husbandry, in general, family resilience is in the high category, as well as from each dimension, all are in the high category. Types of professional work consisting of honorary teachers, Koran teachers and honorary staff generally fall into the high category, whereas when viewed from each dimension, only the physical endurance dimension is in the high category, for the dimensions of economic resilience, social psychological resilience and socio-cultural resilience it is in the medium category with an index value. is below 70.00%. This can provide input to the government to further increase assistance to these occupational groups.

Based on the results of the regression carried out, all independent variables consisting of total income (X1), number of dependents (X2) and number of times receiving JPS Gemilang (X3) partially or simultaneously have no significant effect on physical resilience, economic resilience, social resilience psychology and socio-cultural resilience of the recipients of JPS Gemilang.

REFERENCES

1. Baiquni., 1999, "Critical Reflection on the JPS (Social Safety Net) Program, Case Study of the PDM-DKE Project", JKAP, Vol. 3, No. 1, 1999, Yogyakarta: Gajah Mada University
2. BPS, & PPPA, K. (2016). Development of Family Resilience 2016. Jakarta: Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection.

3. Ferdinand, Augusty. 2012. Management Research Methods. University Publishing Agency. Diponegoro. Semarang.
4. Frankenberger, TR, and MKMcCaston. (1998). The Household Livelihood Security Concept. Food, Nutrition, and Agriculture Journal. 22:30-33.
5. Ministry of Administrative Reform of the Republic of Indonesia. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services. Jakarta: Ministry of Administrative Reform of the Republic of Indonesia; 2009.
6. West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Government, Governor's Decree Number 360 – 405 of 2020 concerning the Status of Emergency Response to Non-Natural Disasters Covid-19. NTB
7. Regulation of the Minister of State for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Number 6 of 2013 concerning the Implementation of Family Development. Jakarta
8. Sunarti, Euis. (2001). Study of Family Resilience and Its Size: A Case Study of Its Effect on Pregnancy Quality. [Dissertation]. Bogor: Bogor Agricultural Institute.

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